

SIGNIFICANCE OF TEMPORARY RESTORATIONS MADE OF SELF-CURING RESIN IN THE MANUFACTURE OF CERAMIC VENEERS

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ABSTRACT

The direct method of fabricating try-in and, if necessary, provisional restorations made of self-hardening resin can be used to obtain perfectly fitting and contoured veneers. This requires a minimum amount of time and materials. Since this method does not involve the preparation of teeth, it allows the patient and the dentist to visually study the treatment plan, which does not exclude the adoption of alternative decisions at the planning stage.

Keywords: temporary restoration of teeth, planning, self-hardening resin, porcelain veneers, minimal preparation.

Restoration of teeth with aesthetic disorders: loss of color, changes in shape, destruction or poor-quality restorations is one of the most popular routine procedures in practical dentistry. The ideal choice in such cases today is indirect restoration of teeth with ceramic veneers. However, all-ceramic veneers may vary in color depending on the condition of the stumps of the prepared abutment teeth. Minimal preparation combined with opaque covering of the abutments allows the natural shade of heavily stained teeth to be recreated to create the natural color depth of porcelain veneers. The clinical success of a minimally invasive porcelain veneer preparation depends not only on the high precision of the impression material, the impression technique and the skill of the dental technician, but mainly on the careful planning phase. Waiting for the results of orthopedic treatment can be stressful for both the patient and the dentist. The esthetic and restorative results of all-ceramic veneers can be determined without tooth preparation using trial resin restorations, which are made with self-curing resin. These plastic restorations are produced by a precise "trial and addition" method, which saves materials and time. They are applied to the restored area of the teeth (before preparation) so that the patient can see the results of the planned treatment in advance, and the doctor can justify the proposed type of prosthetics and take into account the wishes of the patient. This procedure can be carried out repeatedly as the desired result is achieved. Introduction Patients often seek dental care to restore the disturbed appearance of the dentition. But their hopes for a good aesthetic effect after installing the prosthesis do not always come true. In pursuit of restorative goals, orthopedic surgeons should not forget about the aesthetic effect. To predict the results of orthopedic treatment, diagnostic

models with wax reproductions of all-ceramic restorations (WaxUp) were used. Unfortunately, they cannot be used to accurately study the relationship between the lips and soft tissues directly in the restoration area. This deprives the patient and the dentist of the opportunity to fully use the information contained in the diagnostic model with wax modeling of the future restoration [2]. Temporary restorations are also used to determine the results of orthopedic treatment. However, the irreversibility of tooth preparation before the fabrication of a temporary prosthesis is the main disadvantage of traditional restorative methods. The patient benefits if he can form a visual representation of the prosthesis in the restored area even before the preparation of the teeth. This allows the doctor to familiarize the patient with the proposed treatment plan and clearly show the future result. In order to determine in advance the results of the treatment in terms of aesthetics and function, provisional restorations are more often used, imitating future all-ceramic veneers or crowns. They are made from chemically cured acrylic resin by an indirect method (Speeditemp, Prairie Village Pro-stetics). This is a rather laborious, time-consuming and financially expensive process, both for the patient and for the doctor and dental laboratory. The proposed method of using fast-hardening composite plastic from 3M ESPE and KERR manufacturers is quite simple to use and does not cause inconvenience during clinical admission. Try-in restorations created before the preparation of the teeth on the diagnostic model using fast-setting resin can be viewed directly on the prosthetic bed. Manufactured from a diagnostic wax-up, they convey information based on soft tissue, functional chewing and articulation. Their qualities are obvious to both the patient and the doctor. Purpose of the work The purpose of this work is to pre-

sent the method of using try-in restorations, which allow in advance, without tooth preparation, to demonstrate the appearance of future all-ceramic structures. Materials and methods Let's consider the technique on the example of a clinical case. A 40-year-old patient came to the clinic with complaints of insufficient aesthetics, chips and shortening of the front teeth. In the course of a comprehensive examination, the diagnosis was made: generalized pathological abrasion of teeth, combined form II st. . We performed treatment taking into account the clinical situation with the use of frameless restorations in the lateral and anterior sections. Photographs were taken at all stages. All-ceramic veneers were placed to improve the esthetic outcome in order to replace worn and discolored composite restorations and veneers, to correct the color and shape of anterior teeth 1.3, 1.2, 1.1, 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 3.4, 3.3, 3.2, 3.1, 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4. All ceramic veneers were installed by us with strict adherence to technology. Orthopedic treatment began with careful planning. Immediately after the diagnosis was made, anatomical impressions were obtained to make diagnostic models of the jaws and study the shape of the dental arches [1]. The wax reproduction of the future ceramic restoration was reproduced on diagnostic models. This prevents the need to remove facial enamel and makes the procedure "reversible". Next, an impression was obtained from the silicone mass from the surface of the wax diagnostic model [1]. Impressions (silicone keys) were made in advance, before the self-hardening plastic was introduced inside. The teeth to be restored were thoroughly cleaned of soft and hard dental deposits, treated with a chlorhexidine solution, and dried with air [6]. After that, the surface of the impression was isolated with vaseline oil, a self-hardening plastic was introduced into the silicone key and applied to the prepared teeth directly in the oral cavity, allowing it to harden for 5 minutes. As a result, the plastic reproduction was well separated from the impression and turned out to be "sitting" on the teeth. Correction of the appearance of plastic restorations was carried out using a flowable light-curing material of the corresponding color using the "trial and addition" method to obtain an aesthetic and functional optimum of shape and size. Excess material from the plastic restoration was removed with a diamond bur using water cooling. In order to achieve the natural esthetic effect of a fragile plastic restoration, a color shade was added with an appropriate paint and corrected with a flowing light-curing material. After that, the results of treatment were evaluated from the

aesthetic and functional points of view [3-5]. As a result, the design is firmly fixed on the teeth. After the patient approved the treatment plan, the teeth were prepared directly for all-ceramic constructions.

If, nevertheless, a temporary prosthesis is required, then the procedure must be repeated and the temporary prosthesis attached to a small area of enamel etched with acid according to the above method using self-hardening composite resin [3]. Finished all-ceramic restorations were installed on the teeth as they were ready according to the developed fixation protocol. Conclusion It has been proven in practice that the direct method of fabricating try-in and, if necessary, provisional restorations made of self-curing resin can be used to obtain perfectly fitting and contoured fitting and provisional veneers. This requires a minimum amount of time and materials. Since this method does not involve tooth preparation, it allows the patient and the dentist to visually study the treatment plan, which does not preclude alternative decisions at the planning stage.

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